

Life Cycle Assessment Approach, Factors Affecting The Application Of Lca In Enterprises

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 30, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 31, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Lifecycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), Life Cycle Energy Analysis (LCEA)</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6402371</p>	<p><i>This study synthesizes perspectives on Life cycle assessment (LCA) applied in enterprises. The article also analyzes the different approaches of LCA, stating the methods of using LCA based on four types: Life cycle assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), Life Cycle Energy Analysis (LCEA). The article also shows that the application of LCA can help businesses reduce costs, be friendly to the environment, promotes the sustainable development of both companies and society, thereby promoting the voluntary application of LCA. The article also identifies and measures the factors affecting the application of LCA in enterprises, proving that the application of LCA impacts sustainable development in enterprises. Methodology - We collected data on 197 manufacturing enterprises in 6 sectors. This study's main data analysis method is the SEM structural equation modeling method. The article used AMOS software to evaluate and measure the influence of each factor on the application of LCA in enterprises. Practical implications - LCA research has shown that the proper use of resources is essential. Measuring and recording information through product life cycle assessment has also shown that we are disrupting the ecological environment without recreating the environment; we live by capital, not by added value.</i></p>

Introduction

According to Pehnt, Martin (2006), "LCA is a technique for assessing the environmental aspects and potential impacts associated with a product, process or service, by: Aggregation of inputs into energy and related materials and emissions; Assess potential environmental impacts related to identified inputs and emissions; Analyze results to help you make decisions more discerning."

Therefore, it is a technique for assessing the environmental impacts associated with all stages of the product life cycle from raw material extraction through raw material handling, production, distribution, use, repair and maintenance, and disposal or recycling. The results help business leaders decide which products or processes have the most negligible environmental impact.

Research question:

1. How to approach LCA in enterprises?
2. Methods used in LCA?
3. What are the influencing factors, and how much influence does each factor have on applying LCA in enterprises?
4. Impact of LCA and other factors on the sustainable development of enterprises?

The article presents different approaches to LCA: (1) Attributional LCA, Consequential LCA, and social LCA, (2) Approach according to ISO guidelines. We study and demonstrate LCA methods, including Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) which includes "process-based LCAs," economic input-output LCA (EIOLCA), and hybrid approaches; Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA); Life Cycle Energy Analysis (LCEA). We have proven the influencing factors and the degree of influence of each factor on the LCA and the business's sustainable development level.

1. Litterature reviews

Life cycle assessment or LCA (also known as life cycle analysis) is a methodology for assessing the environmental impacts associated with all stages of the life cycle of a commercial product, process, or service. In the case of a manufactured product, the environmental effects are assessed from the extraction and processing of raw materials through the production, distribution, and use of the product, to its recycling or disposal of ingredients that make it up. Common environmental impacts that need to be considered include resource use, human health, and ecological consequences.

According to Gong, Jian; You, Fengqi (2017), LCA is being used to support business strategy and R&D (18% each of the apps surveyed); other uses use LCA as input for a product or process design (15%), educational use

(13%), and use for labeling or product claims (11%). In addition, LCA is continuously integrated into construction practices by developing and implementing appropriate tools — for example, the European ENSLIC Building project guide, which guides trainees to apply LCI data for planning, design, and construction.

Large corporations worldwide are implementing LCA in research and operations. Many governments support the development of national databases to support LCA (Ilgin, Mehmet Ali; Surendra M. Gupta, 2010). Of particular note is the growing use of LCAs for ISO Type III labels known as Environmental Product Claims, where quantified environmental data for a product with established parameter categories previously based on the ISO 14040 series of standards. Third-party certification plays a vital role in today's industry, and third-party certified LCA-based labels are increasingly important for the value assessment environment of the products. In particular, such independent certification shows the company's dedication to providing customers with safe and environmentally friendly products (Kerr, Niall; Gouldson, Andy; Barrett, John, 2017).

The energy technology lifecycle assessment has begun to reflect the interactions between the current grid and future energy technology in recent years. Some papers focus on the energy life cycle, while others focus on carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases. According to Joshua M. Pearce (2008), the primary criticism these sources make is that when considering energy technology, the evolving nature of the power grid must be taken into account. If this is not done, a given energy-grade technology can emit more CO₂ over its lifetime than it has initially been expected to reduce, which is most clearly documented in the case of wind energy.

LCA also has key roles in environmental impact assessment, integrated waste management, and pollution research. Important recent studies applying LCA include: (1) An LCA study that evaluated the economics of an oxygen-enriched air production plant from an ecological design standpoint. (2) Environmental impact assessment of pavement maintenance, repair, and restoration activities (Klopffer, Walter and Birgit Grahl, 2014).

According to Matthews, H. Scott, Chris T. Hendrickson, and Deanna H. Matthews (2014), it is widely accepted that LCA is included in the 14000 series of environmental management standards by the Organization for Standardization. International (ISO), particularly in ISO 14040 and ISO 14044. ISO 14040 provides the 'principles and framework' of the Standard, while ISO 14044 outlines the 'requirements and guidelines.

Figure 1: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) stages diagram

According to R. Kenny, C. Law; J.M. Pearce (2010), the objective of LCA is to thoroughly compare the environmental impacts ascribed to products and services by quantifying all inputs and outputs of material flows and assessing the effects of this feedstock on the environment. The assessment results are used to improve processes and policies that support and provide a solid basis for informed decisions.

3. Theoretical framework of research

3.1. LCA's approaches

LCA should not be seen as a single method but as one of several methods of quantifying results from a different point of view. Among these methods are three main categories: Attributional LCA, Consequential LCA, and Social LCA (McManus, M.C., 2010).

Attributional LCA seeks to attribute the burdens associated with producing and using a particular product, service, or process over a specified period. Attributional LCA aims to determine the environmental consequences of a decision or a proposed change in the system under study and is therefore future-oriented and requires an account of economic and market impacts. In other words, Attributional LCA answers 'how pollutants, resources, and inter-process exchanges are being carried out in the enterprise (Sathre, Roger (2010) while **Consequential LCA** answers the question of how it happens. The third Type of LCA, called "**social**

LCA," is also under development and is a different approach to assessing social impacts. LCA (SLCA) is a helpful tool for companies to identify and evaluate the potential social impacts of a product or service's life cycle on various stakeholders (e.g., employees, employees, etc.), local communities, consumers). SLCA is covered in the UNEP/SETAC's Guidelines for social life cycle assessment of products published in 2009 in Quebec. This tool is built on ISO 26000:2010 Guidelines for Social Responsibility and the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Guidelines.

Some widely recognized procedures for LCA are included in the ISO 14000 series of environmental management standards, in particular, ISO 14040 and 14044; Greenhouse gas (GHG) product life cycle assessments can also comply with specifications such as Publicly Available Specification (PAS) 2050 and the GHG Protocol Life Cycle Accounting and Reporting Standard (J.M. Pearce, 2011)

The ISO LCA standard requires various parameters to be expressed quantitatively and qualitatively, known as study design parameters (SPDs). According to ISO guidelines, the contents of an LCA include:

Product System is the set of processes (input-to-output transformation activities) necessary to perform a defined function and the system boundary. It represents all the processes in the life cycle of a product or process.

Functional unit defines the scope, quantifies the service provided by the system, the scope contains the inputs and outputs, providing the basis for comparing/analyzing alternative goods or services. The functional unit is an essential part of the LCA and should be clearly defined. It is used to select one or more product systems that can provide functionality. The functional unit thus allows different methods to be considered functionally equivalent. The defined available unit must be quantifiable. The functional unit answers the following questions: What? How much? For how long / how many times? Where? How well?

The reference current is the amount of product or energy required to realize the functional unit. Often, reference flows are qualitatively and quantitatively different for different products or systems on the same reference line; however, there are cases where they can be the same.

System boundary, which defines processes, should be included in the product systems analysis.

Assumptions and limitations include any assumptions or decisions made during the study that may affect the final results.

Data quality requirements specify what types of data should be included and what restrictions may apply.

The allocation procedure is used to allocate the inputs and outputs of a product. This procedure is necessary for processes that produce multiple products or co-products. This is also known as the multifunctionality of the product system. ISO 14044 presents a hierarchy of solutions for solving cross-functional problems, as the choice of a co-product allocation method can significantly affect the outcome of the LCA. When using allocation methods, attention should be paid to the following issues:

Avoid Allocation by Sub-Division - this method tries to separate the unit process into smaller sub-processes to separate product production from co-product production

Avoid Allocation through System Expansion (or substitution)- this method attempts to extend the co-product process, identifying sub-functions of the product (or reference product). In other words, the most likely alternative is to produce the co-product independently (System 2). The impacts resulting from the alternative way of having the co-product (System 2) are then subtracted from the determining product to isolate the effects in System 1.

Allocation (or partition) based on Physical Relationship - this method tries to divide inputs and outputs and allocate them based on the physical relationship between products (e.g., mass, energy usage, etc.))

Allocation (or partition) based on Other Relationship (non-physical)- this method tries to divide inputs and outputs and allocate them based on immaterial relationships (e.g., economic value).

Impact assessment, outline, and calculate identified impact categories. Specifically, life cycle inventory data is translated into environmental impacts such as human toxicity, smog, global warming, and eutrophication.

A data Document is a straightforward document of the inputs/outputs (individual streams) used in the research. This is necessary because most analyzes do not consider all inputs and outputs of the product system, thus providing the reader with a transparent representation of the selected data. It also clarifies why system boundaries, product systems, functional units, etc., are chosen.

3.2. Methods of LCA

Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) is concerned with creating an inventory cycle that follows flows from a natural source (biosphere) to a production system. It is the process of quantifying material and energy requirements, atmospheric emissions, soil emissions, water emissions, resource usage, and other emissions over the life of a product or process. In other words, it is the aggregate of all the fundamental flows involved in each process in a product system (Jyotirmay Mathur; Narendra Kumar Bansal; Hermann-Joseph Wagner, 2004).

Developing an inventory is common to start with an engineering system flow model using product system input and output data. The flow model is illustrated by a flow diagram of assessed activities in the supply chain,

giving a clear picture of the boundaries of the engineering system. The input and output data required for model building are collected for all activities within the system boundary.

The output of the LCI is an aggregate of the underlying flows from all the processes in the product system. When collecting data for each function within the system boundary, the ISO LCA standard requires quantitative measurement studies or data estimates to represent each process in the product system. Practitioners should aim to collect data from primary sources (e.g., measuring the inputs and outputs of an on-premises process or other physical means). The questionnaire is often used for on-site data collection and can even be issued to the respective manufacturer or company to complete. Recorded questionnaire items may include Type of product to be collected, data collectors and dates, data collection period, detailed explanation of the process, inputs (raw materials, auxiliary materials, energy...), outputs (emissions to air, water, and land), quantity and quality of inputs and outputs. (Klopffer, Walter and Birgit Grahl, 2014).

Often, primary data collection can be complex, and the business can keep it proprietary or confidential. An alternative to primary data is secondary data, which is data that comes from LCA databases, literature sources, and other past studies. With secondary sources, the information is similar to one process but not exact (e.g., data from another country, another approach, ...). However, secondary data is not always inferior to primary data. For example, one might refer to the data of another study in which the author used the preliminary data very precisely. Along with primary data, secondary data should document the origin, reliability, and representativeness of time, place, and technology.

When defining the inputs and outputs to document each process in an LCI product system, the practitioner may encounter a situation where a function has multiple input streams or generates various output streams. It is necessary to allocate the streams based on the "Allocation Process." In addition, for LCI, supply chain products are those that humans and, typically manufacture, may not have access to data regarding inputs and outputs to processes. Previous production of the product. Therefore, an organization implementing an LCA must turn to secondary sources if it does not already have such data from its previous studies. National databases or datasets included with LCA tools, or which are readily accessible, are familiar sources for such information.

LCI methods include "process-based LCAs," economic input-output LCA (EIO-LCA), and hybrid approaches. Process-based LCAs are a bottom-up LCI approach to building LCIs using knowledge of the industrial processes in a product's lifecycle and the physical flows that connect them. EIO-LCA is a top-down LCI approach and uses information about the underlying flows related to a unit of economic activity across different sectors. This information is usually obtained from national statistics by government agencies that track trade and services between industries. Hybrid LCA is a combination of process-based LCAs and EIO-LCA (Yadav, Surendra; Mishra, Govind, 2021)

The quality of LCI data is often assessed using a pedigree matrix. Different pedigree matrices are available, but all contain several data quality metrics and a set of qualitative criteria for each. Another hybrid approach integrates the widely-used, semi-quantitative approach that uses a pedigree matrix into a qualitative analysis better to illustrate the quality of LCI data for non-technical audiences, particularly policymakers.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) is an inventory analysis of life cycle impact assessment (LCIA). This phase of the LCA aims to assess the potential impacts on the environment and human health due to the baseline flows identified in the LCI. The ISO 14040 and 14044 standards require that the required steps to complete the LCIA are:

Obligatory

Selection of impact categories, category indicators, and feature models: The ISO standard requires a wide selection of impacts covering "a comprehensive set of environmental issues." The consequences must be related to the geographic area of the study and explain the rationale for each selected impact. Usually, the LCIA method is often chosen (e.g. TRACI, ReCiPe, AWARE, etc.).

Classification of Inventory Results: This step assigns LCI results to selected impact items based on their environmental impacts. This is usually accomplished using the LCI database or LCA software. Common impact categories include Global Warming, Ozone Depletion, Acidification, Human Toxicity, etc.

Characterization: which quantitatively transforms the LCI results within each impact category via "characterization factors" (also referred to as equivalency factors) to create "impact category indicators." In other words, this step aims to answer "how much does each result contribute to the impact category?" The primary purpose of this step is to convert all streams classified for an impact into standard units for comparison. For example, for Global Warming, the unit is usually defined as CO₂-equiv or CO₂-e (CO₂ equivalents), where CO₂ is given the value one, and all other units are converted to correspond to the effect. Their related actions.

Optional

Normalize results: This step aims to answer "Is that a lot?" by representing the LCIA result for the selected frame of reference. A separate reference value is usually chosen for each impact type and provides spatial and temporal information that helps confirm the LCIA results. Reference standards are typical impacts by geographic area, population, industry sector, or product system...

Grouping LCIA results: These steps are performed by sorting or ranking the LCIA results into a group or several groups. However, subgrouping is subjective and may not be consistent across studies.

Weight of impact items: This step aims to determine the importance of each category and how important it is compared to others allowing the study to aggregate impact points into a single index for comparison. Weighting is highly subjective and often decided based on stakeholder perspectives. There are three main types of weights: the dashboard method, the currency method, and the target method. ISO 14044 generally does not recommend weights and believes that weights should not be used in LCA studies intended for comparison and public disclosure.

Lifecycle impacts can also be classified according to the multiple stages of a product's development, production, use, and disposal. These impacts can be divided into primary, use, and end-of-life effects. The immediate results include extraction of raw materials, production (conversion of raw materials into products), transportation of products to markets or locations, construction/installation, and initiation of use. Usage impacts include the physical effects of operating the product (such as energy, water, etc.) and any maintenance, renovation, or repair required to continue using the product.

Life Cycle Energy Analysis (LCEA)

Life Cycle Energy Analysis (LCEA) is an approach in which all energy inputs to a product are taken into account, not only energy inputs directly in the manufacturing process, but also all energy inputs required to produce the components, materials, and services as are necessary for the manufacturing process. An earlier term for this method was energy analysis. With LCEA, the total life cycle input is established.

Energy production

It can be seen that a lot of energy is lost in the production process, such as nuclear power, photovoltaics, or high-quality petroleum products. The net energy content is the energy content of the product minus the input energy used in extraction and conversion, directly or indirectly. A controversial early result by the LCEA claimed that producing solar cells required more power than could be recovered using solar cells, but the results were disproved. Currently, the energy payback time of photovoltaic solar panels ranges from several months to several years. Recycling the module can further reduce the energy payback time to about a month. Another new concept that comes from life cycle assessment is energy cannibalism. Energy cannibalism refers to an effect in which the rapid growth of an entire energy-intensive industry creates a demand for the energy used by existing power plants. Therefore, in the process of rapid development, considering the whole industry does not generate energy because new energy is used to power the future power plants. Work has been carried out in the U.K. to determine several renewable technologies' lifecycle energy impact (along with full LCA). (Hammond, Geoffrey P., 2004).

Energy Recovery

If the material is burned during disposal, the energy released during combustion can be harnessed and used to produce electricity. This provides a low-impact energy source, especially when compared to coal and natural gas. Although incineration produces more greenhouse gas emissions than landfills, waste plants are well equipped with regulatory pollution control devices to minimize this negative impact. A study comparing energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions from landfills (without energy recovery) versus incineration (with energy recovery) found that incineration is superior except when landfill gas is recovered to produce electricity (Damgaard, Anders; Riber, Christian; Fruergaard, Thilde; Hulgaard, Tore; Christensen, Thomas H. (July 2010).

4. Research on factors affecting the application of LCA in enterprises

4.1. Research sample

We surveyed 197 businesses through an online questionnaire to identify and measure the factors affecting LCA adoption in Vietnam using AMOS data analysis software. Survey respondents are representatives of the board of directors of enterprises, technical experts, production workers, accounting, and corporate governance experts. The survey and data collection period is from February 2021 to December 2021. This study's primary data analysis method is the structural equation modeling (SEM) method with AMOS - SPSS. To obtain a reliable estimate for this method, according to Tauchen (1986), the sample should usually be more significant than 200 ($n > 200$). Based on the empirical rule of Hair et al. (2010), for one estimator, the minimum sample size needed for this study is $n > 8 \times \text{number of variables} = 8 \times 23 = 184$. Combining the above principles, the sample size, we choose with $n = 197$.

No.	Scope of activity	Number of firms	Proportion
1	Rubber processing	23	11.7%
2	Mineral	42	21.3%
3	Plastic packaging	32	16.2%
4	Fertilizer	19	9.6%
5	Steel manufacturing	26	13.2%
6	Food processing	55	27.9%
Total		197	100%

4.2. Identify and measure factors affecting the application of LCA in enterprises

4.2.1. Research model and hypothesis

According to the study, the application of LCA is affected by the legal system related to LCA, product manufacturing process characteristics, business development strategy, enterprise accounting system, and business characteristics. (Allen, SR; Hammond, GP; Harajli, HA; Jones, CI; McManus, MC; Winnett, AB (May 2008) At the same time, the paper also proves that LCA application affects the sustainability of the business.

Figure 1- Model of research

Table 1 – Variables affecting the application of LCA and the level of sustainability of the business

	Legal regulatory system related to LCA (L.R.)
1	Timeliness and suitability of the legal document system related to LCA (LR1)
2	Completeness of legal documents related to LCA (LR2)
3	The enforcement of the legal system of legal documents related to LCA (LR3)
	Characteristics of manufacture process (CP)
4	Characteristics of materials used (CP1)
5	Production stages can be segregated (CP2)
6	The product life cycle is relatively long (CP3)
7	Can track and record information in the product life cycle (CP4)
	The strategy of the business (S.B.)
8	Strategies for effective use of resources require businesses to apply LCA (SB1)
9	Clean production strategy requires businesses to apply LCA (SB2)
10	Ensuring the interests of stakeholders requires businesses to apply LCA (SB3)
	Characteristics of the business (C.B.)
11	Production technology is updated with LCA (CB1)
12	Managers' competencies ensure the application of LCA (CB2)
13	Information systems ensure the application of LCA (CB3)
14	Tools and methods of measuring inputs and outputs to enable LCA measurement (CB4)
	Enterprise accounting system (A.C.)
15	The level of accounting staff of the enterprise is capable of applying LCA (AC1)
16	Accounting information system ensures LCA application (AC2)
17	Application of modern technology ensures LCA application (AC3)
	Applying LCA (LCA) (Dependent variable)
18	Using LCI (LCA1)
19	Using LCIA (LCA2)
20	Use LCEA (LCA3)
	Level sustainability of business (SUS) (Dependent variable)
21	Economically sustainable (SUS1)
22	Social sustainability (SUS2)
23	Environmentally sustainable (SUS3)

AC1							.935
AC3							.717
AC2							.619

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Pattern Matrix rotation matrix is used to analyze factor confirmatory in AMOS software, to see whether the elements are convergent and discriminant.

Table 4 - Regression Weights

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
LCA	<---	SB	.332	.089	3.729	***	
LCA	<---	CB	.038	.088	.435	.054	
LCA	<---	CP	.105	.119	.884	.002	
LCA	<---	AC	.218	.089	2.456	.014	
LCA	<---	LR	.434	.104	4.185	***	
SUS	<---	LR	-.033	.111	-.302	.763	
SUS	<---	AC	.011	.091	.119	.003	
SUS	<---	CP	.240	.122	<u>3.966</u>	.041	
SUS	<---	CB	.354	.092	3.837	***	
SUS	<---	SB	.214	.095	2.247	.025	
SUS	<---	LCA	.367	.098	3.767	***	

Regression Weights results (Table 4) show that: independent variables S.B. (Strategy of business), C.P. (Characteristics of manufacture process), and A.C. (enterprise accounting system), L.R. (legal regulatory system) have an impact on LCA (sig < 0.05). Hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H5 are accepted. The independent variables C.B. (Characteristics of the business) do not affect LCA (sig > 0.05). Hypotheses H4 are rejected. Similarly, variables A.C., CP, C.B., S.B., LCA impact the dependent variable SUS (sig < 0.05). Hypotheses H7, H8, H9, H10, H11 are accepted. The independent variable L.R. (Legal regulatory system) does not affect SUS (sig > 0.05). Hypothesis H6 is rejected.

Table 5- Squared Multiple Correlations

Estimate	Estimate	Estimate	Estimate
SUS .407	LCA .428	CP3 .486	CP4 .477
AC3 .587	AC2 .452	CP2 .630	CP1 .582
SUS1 .604	AC1 .750	CB1 .694	CB2 .676
SUS2 .669	SUS3 .670	CB4 .733	CB3 .570
LR1 .683	LR3 .615	SB4 .664	SB3 .719
LCA1 .780	LR2 .650	SB2 .739	SB1 .685
LCA3 .653	LCA2 .714	LCA3 .653	
	LCA3 .653		

Table 6 - Standardized Regression Weights

	Estimate
LCA <--- SB	.334
LCA <--- CP	.493
LCA <--- AC	.225
LCA <--- LR	.385
SUS <--- AC	.012
SUS <--- CP	.222
SUS <--- CB	.381
SUS <--- SB	.423
SUS <--- LCA	.582

Standardized Regression Weights results (Table 6) show that:

Impact on LCA: The independent variable C.P. has the most substantial impact with 0.493, followed by L.R. (0.385), S.B. (0.334); C.B. has no impact.

Impact on SUS: The intermediate variable LCA has the most substantial effect with 0.582, followed by S.B. (0.423), C.B. (0.381), CP (0.222). L.R. has no impact.

The summary results of the influences of factors on the application of G.A. and the sustainability of business are as follows:

Figure 2 – The influences of factors on the application of LCA and the sustainability of the business

5. Conclusion:

Product life cycle environmental impact assessment is a systematic technique for identifying, quantifying, examining, and evaluating information from life cycle and life cycle impact assessments.

Some studies are against the LCA approach, such as on the consistency of the methodology, especially concerning system boundaries and the vulnerability of LCAs, without a formal set of requirements and guidelines. LCA is based on the practitioner's perspective and opinion-based methodologies. The limitations of LCA when it comes to focusing only on the ecological aspects of sustainability, not the economic or social factors. This has distinguished it from product flow analysis (PLA) and similar methods.

We have proven the influencing factors and the degree of influence of each element on the LCA and the business's sustainable development level. Independent variables S.B. (Strategy of the company), C.P. (Characteristics of manufacture process), and A.C. (enterprise accounting system), L.R. (legal regulatory system) have an impact on LCA. The independent variables C.B. (Business characteristics) do not affect LCA. Similarly, variables A.C., CP, C.B., S.B., LCA impact the dependent variable. The independent variable L.R. (Legal regulatory system) does not affect SUS. The independent variable C.P. has the most decisive impact with 0.493, followed by L.R. (0.385), S.B. (0.334); C.B. has no effect. The intermediate variable LCA has the most substantial impact with 0.582, followed by S.B. (0.423), C.B. (0.381), CP (0.222). L.R. has no impact.

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